

GUIDE TO THE ECOREFIBRE RESULTS IN BRIEF AND PROJECT INNOVATION FACTSHEETS

This scheme guides the reader through the EcoReFibre Results in Brief and Factsheets developed around the project demonstrations. To find the publication you are interested in, search by title or partner logo on the project website or on Zenodo.

1

Estimating the resource

Estimating post-consumer fibreboard waste generation in Europe

Defines the scale and future availability of the resource.

2

Sorting

A sorting line for separating wood waste into usable fractions for new wood-based panels

Creates cleaner streams of post-consumer solid wood and fibreboard for later recovery steps.

3

Fibres and fines recovery

Extraction of wood fibres from post-consumer fibreboard (wet process)
Extraction of wood fines from post-consumer fibreboard (dry process)

Defibration of solid wood waste and post-consumer fibreboard (the mTMP PROCESS)

Bridges sorting and new products by producing secondary raw materials.

4

New products with recycled content

Recycling post-consumer fibres from wood waste into new fibreboards

Recycling post-consumer fibres from wood waste into new insulation products

Recycling post-consumer fibreboard waste into new particleboard

Shows where recovered fibres and fines can return to use.

5

By-products valorisation

Bioblocks: construction material made from wood fibreboard dust

Completes the cascade by giving value to the smallest residual fraction.